

NFDI 4
BIODIVERSITY
BIODIVERSITY, ECOLOGY & ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

NFDI4Biodiversity - Training and Education Report

for Consortia Progress Report

National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

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NFDI4Biodiversity training and education

Through supporting exceptional competencies in data management, collaborating with stakeholders, and promoting awareness, our training and education activities drive a cultural change for more effective data management in biodiversity research, adhering to the principles of good scientific practice.

Sustainable Structures

The training coordinator oversees training activities, governed by the Steering Committee and SIG3 Training. Strategic collaborations with external organisations, create synergies and effective marketing strategies enhance the visibility and attractiveness of training offers and materials.

Available Training Offers

The NFDI4Biodiversity partner organisations jointly provide a comprehensive, needs-based, modular, and scalable training portfolio for researchers, students, and data scientists. It includes various training formats combining generic Research Data Management (RDM) skills with domain-specific topics. To aid educators in integrating data literacy and RDM into university curricula, Open Educational Resources (OER) are provided for integration into lectures.

Implementation and Utilisation

In the last three years (2020- 2023), we have organised over 40 lectures and workshops with more than 800 participants. These events, tailored to specific topics, skill levels, user categories, and data types, have enriched our training portfolio in five training modules (see Figure). Our collaborative endeavors with service providers and partner institutions, through Task Areas (TA) and Measures (M), have successfully brought these offerings to life.

Impact on Partner Institutions

The training activities address specific challenges, such as legal aspects, and common training events like the Winter School 2022, foster collaboration, networking, and the integration of diverse perspectives and expertise. NFDI4Biodiversity training events and materials integrate partner data and various tools and services e.g. BEXIS2, BIIGLE, DMP Tool, Data Submission Service, DWB, RightField, VAT.

Quality of Services

The NFDI4Biodiversity quality management follows best practices of relevant initiatives such as Hessian Research Data Infrastructures (HeFDI) and German Initiative for Network Information (DINI). Continuous quality control, user feedback, and performance reviews ensure the training is tailored, well-defined, and meets community standards.

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1. Executive Summary

Training and education activities, both in NFDI4Biodiversity and throughout the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), i.e. within the NFDI Section Training and Education (Section EduTrain) are supposed to "[...] enhance the formal quality of the resource "data" so that it can be used for both knowledge creation and the development of sustainable solutions to societal challenges [...]" [1].

Over the past three years, NFDI4Biodiversity has made significant achievements in promoting good data management practices and fostering collaboration among its partners through its training activities.

Available Training Offers:

The NFDI4Biodiversity consortium offers a comprehensive, needs-based, modular, and scalable training portfolio for researchers, students, and data scientists. It includes various training formats such as Seasonal Schools, workshops, and lectures covering generic Research Data Management (RDM) skills with domain-specific topics.

Implementation and Utilisation:

The training portfolio adopts a modular approach, optimising each module for specific content, competence level, user group, and data type. The training portfolio is implemented through the collaboration of various Task Areas (TA) and Measures (M) within the NFDI4Biodiversity community. Training events are organised by service providers, partner institutions, and trainers. The Jupyter Notebook environment, YouTube Channel, NFDI4Biodiversity website and the publication of Open Educational Resources (OER) facilitate training delivery, easy access and reuse.

Quality of Services:

Quality management is emphasised through collaboration with the service coordinator and community-based standards. The NFDI4Biodiversity quality management follows best practices based on approaches of relevant initiatives such as Hessian Research Data Infrastructures (HeFDI) and German Initiative for Network Information (DINI). Continuous quality control, user feedback, and performance reviews ensure the training is tailored, well-defined, and meets biodiversity research standards.

Sustainable Structures:

A training coordinator oversees the coordination and monitoring of training activities, while the governance of training activities is handled by the Steering Committee and the Special Interest Group Training and Education (SIG3 Training). NFDI4Biodiversity training activities are supported by an annual budget to cover event costs, external trainers, and materials. Strategic collaborations with external organisations are pursued to create synergies and avoid duplication of efforts. Marketing strategies are employed to increase visibility, accessibility, and attractiveness of training offers and materials.

Impact on Partner Institutions:

Training activities have a positive impact on partner institutions by addressing specific challenges such as workshops on legal aspects and sharing experiences through workshops and events. Further, the consortium supports partners in their training efforts and resources by developing common training events such as the Winter School 2022. Training activities foster collaboration and networking among different domains and encourage the integration of diverse perspectives and expertise. NFDI4Biodiversity training events and materials integrate data from partners and training on various tools and services, including data management planning (DMP), data submission, and

more. By aligning training with the specific needs of the community and the incorporation of the partners expertise, the portfolio contributes to the advancement of research and education in the field of biodiversity. To assist educators in integrating data literacy and RDM into universities curricula, OER such as videos and slides are provided that can be integrated into lectures. Further, a Self-Learning Unit (SLU) is currently developed by our partner network to empower individuals studying at their own pace and to encourage lecturers integrating Research Data Management and Data Literacy into university curricula.

The consortium organised several cutting-edge training formats and created training materials to empower researchers and practitioners in the field of biodiversity research. These training activities covered topics such as data management and standards, legal aspects, and emerging technologies. Furthermore, we have aligned training content from various existing German and European communities, e.g. de.NBI [2], ELIXIR [3], FAIRDOM [4], Federal State Initiatives (bw2FDM [5], HeFDI [6], TKFDM [7], UBRA [8]).

The NFDI4Biodiversity training activities developed in the first three years were aimed at researchers with different levels of expertise (beginners, advanced, experts). The consortium organised over 40 lectures and workshops with over 800 participants (Table 1, status July 2023). Classroom and online training courses are offered to teach general RDM topics as well as tools and services provided by partners. The consortium organised a highly successful Seasonal School (Winter School 2022), bringing together experts and Early-Career-Researchers to exchange knowledge and skills related to biodiversity data management. Additionally, a series of workshops on legal aspects provided valuable insights into the legal framework surrounding biodiversity research, ensuring compliance and ethical practices. Workshops focused on diverse topics, ranging from data analysis techniques to biodiversity informatics, empowering participants with practical skills and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations. Extensive training activities were developed to familiarise researchers with tools and technologies used in biodiversity research, facilitating efficient data collection, analysis, and sharing. To enhance accessibility and knowledge dissemination, NFDI4Biodiversity developed informative video tutorials, enabling researchers to navigate various aspects of biodiversity data management effectively. Lastly, the project featured individual lectures dedicated to RDM, emphasising best practices and highlighting the importance of data preservation, integrity, and reproducibility at various institutions within the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium and beyond.

By providing essential skills and knowledge, the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium has empowered researchers and practitioners in biodiversity research and contributes to the advancement of biodiversity research, conservation, and policy-making. In this way, the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium has achieved significant milestones over the past three years. This report describes the implementation of our training measures and activities together with our partners.

2. Goals of the training portfolio

“Dedicated to mobilising biodiversity and environmental data for collective use” [9], NFDI4Biodiversity has set six project goals to enable access to decentralised data: 1. promote RDM as an integral part of biodiversity research, 2. enable data FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) [10], 3. add quality to FAIRness, 4. integrate NFDI4Biodiversity into national and international activities, 5. collaborate on NFDI-wide cross-cutting topics, and 6. jointly manage the NFDI as a service infrastructure, making it dynamic and sustainable (project proposal 2019). **The training and education activities aim at implementing these goals by supporting outstanding competencies concerning management of data diversity in the biodiversity research and data management communities.** By building awareness, providing training and education, and collaborating with stakeholders, we strongly drive the cultural change towards more effective data management practices in biodiversity research committed to the rules of good scientific practice. Furthermore, educational activities prepare future generations to foster practices of FAIR data and research data management and help to promote a transparent culture of open science in compliance with ethical and legal standards. Thus, it is our top strategic goal to establish FAIR research data management competencies as a core topic in undergraduate and graduate curricula at German universities by supporting lecturers with low-threshold training offers such as training material or lectures/workshops.

The current work programme and grant covers the period October 2020 to September 2025. Three primary objectives were focused in that period to foster a highly skilled and interdisciplinary community of researchers and data collectors:

- a) Identify the specific knowledge and skill gaps within the biodiversity research community by conducting a thorough **community-based needs assessment** among our partners and evaluate existing training offerings to determine their relevance and potential areas for improvement.
- b) **Develop and test innovative training formats** that cater to the identified gaps and emerging trends in biodiversity research.
- c) Consolidate the services and demands of the co-applicants and participants as part of the biodiversity community by **developing a coherent training portfolio**.

By addressing these objectives, the consortium strived to provide a comprehensive and community oriented training portfolio to enhance technical expertise, expand knowledge on data collection and analysis techniques, as well as fostering an understanding of cutting-edge technologies in biodiversity research. Moreover, NFDI4Biodiversity aims to promote open and FAIR data principles through education, emphasising the importance of data sharing, standardisation, and long-term preservation.

All strategic decisions and developments in NFDI4Biodiversity training and education aim to be embedded in NFDI cross-cutting topics such as Section EduTrain. Members of all consortia collaborate within these Sections to develop standards across research domains. This collaborative approach ensures that the training portfolio aligns with the diverse demands and interests within the biodiversity community ultimately providing a unified and coherent set of services and offerings. Furthermore, it contributes to the NFDI strategy, forming an overarching infrastructure. NFDI4Biodiversity seeks to address the challenges of managing and utilising biodiversity data effectively, “guided by the knowledge that stakeholders in science, politics, nature conservation and landscape management

need reliable data to be able to develop better contributions to the conservation of biodiversity” [9].

3. State of the Art and NFDI4Biodiversity community output

Recognizing the need for reliable data in various domains such as science, politics, nature conservation, and landscape management, NFDI4Biodiversity emerges as a pivotal consortium within the NFDI. The consortium consists of 50 scientific institutions, museums, natural history societies, state offices, and other institutes and expert groups. The combined expertise of the partner network ranges from microbial to plant and animal biodiversity and includes universities and research performing organisations as well as the seven natural science collections for bio- and geodiversity data, who are members of the GFBio datacenter group [11]. Additionally, the partners expertise in bioinformatics and their capability to build and maintain advanced cyberinfrastructure are crucial assets to support biodiversity data storage, processing, and analysis. The partners provide training offers regarding their expertise to other members but also to target groups outside the network ([Supplementary Table 1](#)). The consortium's dedication to data management and analysis is evident through the array of tools and services they provide, such as BEXIS2 [12], BIIGLE [13], DMP Tool [14], Data Submission Service [15], DWB [16], RightField [17], VAT [18]. These tools facilitate data curation, integration, and exploration, enhancing the overall quality and utility of biodiversity data as part of NFDI4Biodiversity training.

a. State of the Art

In the pursuit of good data management practices, it is often recognized that there is a lack of capacity for their implementation and individual, not necessarily FAIR-compliant, workflows are used. Despite the growing importance of data management, the resources and support required to establish and maintain robust systems are often insufficient. NFDI4Biodiversity, with its comprehensive approach, aims to address this challenge by providing not only technical solutions but also guidance and support to ensure the successful implementation of data management practices. Data for biodiversity research comprise various types. Data from experimental studies, automatic device recording, field observations, collection data, taxon-level data, literature, descriptions, sequence data are just a few examples of data collected in this manifold research domain. However, data collection is often done by students and young researchers without much data management experience. As a speciality in biodiversity research a considerable amount of data is collected by citizen scientists and (semi-)professionals, which may not even have their data digitised. As stated in the mission statement NFDI4Biodiversity strives to support structured digital data acquisition, remove technical hurdles in data mobilisation, and eliminate deficiencies, inconsistencies, and incompatibilities in data structures and semantics which impede effective interoperability and re-use of data [9]. NFDI4Biodiversity builds upon the work by the German Research Foundation-funded (DFG) GFBio project, a network of 20 German institutions which had been developing a portfolio of data and data management services for the biodiversity research community since 2014. GFBio encompassed technical, organisational, financial, and community aspects to raise awareness for research data management in biodiversity research and environmental sciences. To sustain the tools and services developed in the GFBio -project, GFBio e.V. was founded in 2016 and is now the coordinating partner of NFDI4Biodiversity. Also, many of the original project partners are co-applicants and

participants in NFDI4Biodiversity. The GFBio project engaged extensively with the biodiversity community through various activities. This included organising over 45 roadshows in Germany, attended by more than 800 researchers for in-depth discussions. Expert round tables, training events, and participation in workshops and conferences were also part of their outreach efforts. They distributed promotional material and engaged in social media activities. A survey on research data management perspectives reached scientists from different subdisciplines. GFBio's help desk and ticket system received over 300 user requests since 2016, providing assistance in DMPs and research data management.

After the start of the NFDI4Biodiversity project, further needs assessment was done through interviews with use case partners and screening of initial use cases status reports (TA1M1 and TA1M4). The status reports were used to discuss possible corporations and to identify needs for support. The results of the GFBio user survey and help desk requests as well as the status reports were the basis for an informed planning of the data management support and efficient user engagement strategy in NFDI4Biodiversity.

b. NFDI4Biodiversity community output

The NFDI4Biodiversity consortium partners organised several cutting-edge training formats and created diverse training material to empower researchers and practitioners in the field of biodiversity research. The training activities covered various topics, including data management, legal aspects and emerging technologies. In the last three years, we exemplified the consolidation of training offers and materials from different sub communities.

Establishing FAIR research data management at universities curricula still remains the top strategic goal but our approach has now shifted towards needs-oriented offers based on practical experiences and real-world applicability during the first three project years. Teaching actors and curriculum developers has shown that initial, low-threshold support is crucial to effectively integrate such topics into university curricula.

This support can cover diverse aspects and formats such as OER, Train-the-Trainer workshops, legal workshops, or an RDM competencies matrix. By providing these resources, we aim to equip educators with the necessary tools and knowledge, ensuring successful implementation in their teaching practices. GFBio e.V. actively supports cross-cutting training programs such as *Data Train* provided by U Bremen Research Alliance (UBRA) and the graduate program *MarMic* provided by International Max Planck Research School of Marine Microbiology (IMPRS) as well as the *FDM-Zertifikatskurs* by State Initiative for Research Data Management North Rhine-Westphalia (fdm.nrw). However, in the end it is still up to the university and the individual lecturer to integrate these topics as an obligatory part of the curricula.

One of the flagship training events organised by NFDI4Biodiversity was the Winter School on Data Management in Ecology and Environmental Science [19], which took place in December 2022. The Winter School has proven to be an effective training event for professionals and gained much attention in the community. 130 applications on 20 places showed that the Winter School 2022 fulfilled a great need for domain specific training offers. The curriculum targeted Early-Career-Researchers with a background in biodiversity and environmental science. It was developed in cooperation with the Ecological Society of Germany, Austria and Switzerland (GfÖ) and combined general RDM topics along the Data

Life Cycle (DLC) (e.g. FAIR data, data literacy) as well as discipline specific topics (e.g. taxonomic harmonisation, data visualisation, data publication, metadata standards) with commonly used tools and services such as Jupyter, R, Python, RightField, and the GFBio DMP Tool. Experts from our consortium partners GFBio e.V., GfÖ, HITS, University Leipzig, University Bremen/PANGAEA, Senckenberg, University Göttingen, and the University Kassel delivered lectures, conducted hands-on workshops, and facilitated interactive sessions, fostering a dynamic learning environment. In terms of learning environment, the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI) cloud service was used to provide a Jupyter notebook, set up by our partners from UFZ Halle. Jupyter is an open-source web application that allows users to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualisations, and narrative text [20]. It supports a wide range of programming languages, including Python, R, and Julia, and is widely used in data science and scientific research. Participants and lecturers used Jupyter notebooks to explore and analyse training data sets deriving from the PlantHub (TA1M1) Use Case from our partner iDiv and software tools for R and Python provided by our partners PANGAEA and SGN to explore data. The implementation of real data from the Use Case could further illustrate the trained concepts on real case studies and mark a significant milestone in the project's progress ([Section 6.c](#)). The curriculum of this Winter School is provided as a template in order to support other consortia and institutions that want to organise similar events [19].

Table 1 Collection of KPIs for the years 2021- July 2023

The following table shows the number of events organised and videos produced as well as the number of participants and video calls. The data cover the period between January 2021 to July 2023. The events 2023 include five events that are already planned for July to November 2023 but are not reflected by the number of participants. The detailed event list can be found in [Supplementary Table 3](#).

KPI	2021		2022		2023	
	Events	Participants	Events	Participants	Events	Participants
Winter School			1	21		
Support of external training program	2	25	5	163	5	146
Individual event	4	56	3	83	6	113
Training on Legal aspects	1	40	2	46	1	
Workshop on Tools and Services	3	78	4	54	4	71
Total	10	199	15	367	16	330
	Uploads	Views	Uploads	Views	Uploads	Views
Videos	17	796	10	1270	19	1361

In addition to this flagship event, NFDI4Biodiversity partner organisations (GFBio e.V., PANGAEA/Uni Bremen, University Kassel, University Jena) cooperated to offer specialised training workshops in 2022 and 2023 on a regular basis at universities throughout Germany. These events cater to different skill levels and address specific topics, such as DMP, data sharing practices, and RDM tools. The training events feature hands-on exercises, case studies, and practical demonstrations to ensure participants can apply their learnings directly to their research projects.

They were requested e.g. by Institute for Chemistry and Biology of the Marine Environment (ICBM) Oldenburg in January 2022/2023, GEOMAR Kiel in February 2023, Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg (BTU) in May 2023 via the NFDI4Biodiversity helpdesk and are an example of the added value of our training modules for the biodiversity community ([Supplementary Table 3](#)).

In July 2021 and May 2022 workshops on legal aspects were organised by our partner University Marburg, based on issues of interest identified in use case interviews (TA1M1) and with partners. These workshops covered a range of legal topics in biodiversity and environmental science including the German Environmental Information Act (Umweltinformationsgesetz), copyright, licences, Nagoya protocol. By attending these workshops, the participants gained a better understanding of their legal obligations and are better equipped to navigate legal challenges that govern national and international data sharing practices. They further served the opportunity to talk about good practices and lessons learned with professional support from our expert Johannes Franke from the Independent Institute for Environmental Issues (UfU).

A SLU [21], created in the context of HeFDI, is currently adapted to domain-specific needs. The HeFDI-SLU has already proven useful to equip researchers with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively manage their data throughout the research lifecycle. University Marburg, together with GFBio e.V. and University Göttingen, now develop a version specifically designed for biodiversity related research, incorporating European life sciences infrastructure (ELIXIR) materials and aligning with GFBio resources. The SLU will provide support in navigating relevant tools and technologies for data management and will empower researchers to handle their data efficiently and in compliance with legal and ethical requirements. It will offer a comprehensive range of resources, including online modules and training materials, to promote best practices in data organisation, documentation, storage, and sharing. Researchers will be able access guidance on DMP, data protection, ethical considerations, and data preservation. The target audience for the course includes students, doctoral candidates, and researchers who seek their first introduction to research data management. This transformation of a SLU from a university/state initiative into a domain-specific learning unit, exemplifies the consolidation of learning materials. It will be constantly updated regarding future needs and trends within the biodiversity community.

The de.NBI Spring School [22] is another significant community event where participants could benefit from the expertise from the NFDI4Biodiversity network. The Spring School took place at the partner institution IPK and was organised by de.NBI, the German ELIXIR node. GFBio e.V. and the data publisher PANGAEA organised two hands-on workshops on Research Data Management, DMP and Data Publishing. The de.NBI e.V. [23] (founded in 2022) has joined the consortium in 2023 as a participant to further strengthen this cooperation. During the de.NBI Spring School 2023. GFBio e.V. and PANGAEA have teamed up with other consortia, such as PUNCH4NFDI and NFDI4Microbiota, to offer a comprehensive training program. Participants did have the opportunity to learn about the various tools and services offered by the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium, such as the GFBio DMP Tool; Data Submission Service and data publication via our data centres PANGAEA and e!DAL-PGP.

RDM training was provided regularly in cooperation with other partner networks, such as the Federal Ministry of Education and Research-funded (BMBF) research

initiative Research initiative for the conservation of biodiversity (FEa) [24] or the project Biogeochemical processes and Air–sea exchange in the Sea–Surface microlayer (BASS) at the University Oldenburg [25]. This support extends beyond the network, showcasing the collaborative and inclusive nature of NFDI4Biodiversity's efforts. By assisting both partner institutions and external organisations, NFDI4Biodiversity promotes the adoption of standardised data management practices and fosters a culture of open science and interdisciplinary collaboration in the field of biodiversity research.

Further, co-operations with partner institutions, such as ZMT, are planned. ZMT focuses on investigating tropical and subtropical coastal ecosystems and their importance for nature and humans. ZMT is working with partners in tropical countries to create a scientific basis for the protection and sustainable use of these ecosystems. ZMT trains students and doctoral candidates to build a community of researchers and practitioners who can continue to advance knowledge and solutions in this field. In NFDI4Biodiversity, ZMT developed tools and services [26] for data management in the context of a flexfunds project. Training for these tools and services will be organised in cooperation with TA1M4.

These training offers form the NFDI4BioDiversity training portfolio, which is described in detail in the following [Section 4](#). By providing diverse and comprehensive training opportunities, NFDI4BioDiversity empowers researchers to acquire essential skills and knowledge, fostering their ability to contribute meaningfully to biodiversity research, conservation, and policy-making.

Beyond training activities, conference participation was an effective strategy for reaching multiplier communities and disseminating information and knowledge to a wider audience. It offers a platform for experts and professionals to share their expertise and insights, while also allowing multipliers to access the latest research findings. We actively engaged in community conferences, like the GfÖ Annual Conference 2022 in Metz (France) focusing on teaching RDM skills and establishing national and international networking opportunities ([Section 6.c](#)).

Moreover, we made significant contributions to cross-cutting topics, demonstrating our commitment to interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. Members of the TA1M4 supported the Section EduTrain, ensuring communication and consolidation of training strategies across research domains, and also backed the platform [forschungsdaten.info](#), promoting open and accessible research data. By participating in these activities, We facilitated the integration of diverse perspectives and expertise from various domains, fostering professional development and encouraging broader cooperation for the advancement of research and education.

4. Designing a community oriented NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio

The NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio is designed to provide a needs-based, modular and scalable framework aligned with the Section EduTrain. It includes generic RDM skills based on the RDM competencies matrix and domain-specific topics. Existing offers are integrated into the concept, and needs-based offers for different competence levels are developed in collaboration with partner organisations.

To ensure a strong focus and consolidation, partner institutions' emphasised areas are incorporated into the training portfolio. Cross-cutting activities and collaborations with various institutions and organisations are fostered to integrate national and international developments in the field.

The training modules are based on individual target groups:

1. *Teaching with data*

The integration of data provided by our partners into teaching benefits participants. Case studies, discipline-specific concepts, data literacy, and FAIR concepts are taught using these data sets, providing valuable resources for learning about biodiversity-related topics.

2. *Training for tools*

NFDI4Biodiversity provides regular and on-demand training to support researchers and data scientists with tools and services for data management and transformation. Training is provided by service providers and experienced users, tailored to individual needs, ensuring effective utilisation of the software.

3. *Train the trainer*

Train the trainer events and open-source slides assist educators in integrating data literacy education into their curricula, building capacity, and ensuring effective teaching.

Four key aspects were identified to ensure the successful transfer of high-quality knowledge and tools developed in the consortium to the community (Figure 1):

1. Program development, 2. Quality management 3. Resources, and 4. Marketing.

The development of a modular, scalable training concept promotes the delivery of needs-based and audience-specific training modules on data literacy by addressing method, community, and skill level. By breaking down the training process into smaller modules, each module can be optimised for a specific content, competence level, user group and data type, that can be trained independently and scaled up as needed. Thus, it improves the efficiency of training activities by allowing dynamic content development regarding the needs of users and availability of lecturers.

Figure 1: Key aspects for transferring knowledge and tools to the community

This figure illustrates the four key aspects contributing to the NFDI4Biodiversity training and education portfolio (coloured boxes). Each field is further defined by topics that were taken into account when developing the training and education portfolio.

a. Program development

The training portfolio is based on a needs assessment of the GFBio project in 2017 as well as requests from the NFDI4Biodiversity partner network through several organisational structures (Task Areas Measures e.g. TA1M1, TA1M2, TA1M4, TA3M1, TA4M4; SIG3 Training, Steering Committee) as described in [Section 5](#). In addition, requests from the helpdesk and feedback from events such as the GfÖ Conference 2022 and NFDI4Biodiversity All-Hands-Conference 2022 were taken into account. The feedback gathered is documented in an inventory of existing materials and resources at our internal project platform Confluence. This inventory includes materials and resources from other RDM initiatives and projects.

The development of an NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio includes establishing the necessary infrastructure to support training delivery. This infrastructure includes determining the resources required, such as facilities, equipment, and software, as well as identifying any constraints that may affect the delivery of the training portfolio. To plan and implement training together within the NFDI4Biodiversity network, the shared project management platforms Confluence and Jira are used for coordination, cooperation, and communication. Through these platforms, training activities, including materials, are documented, and a forum is created for discussion and exchange of experiences. Another important infrastructure that has proven to be particularly useful in the delivery of the NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio is the Jupyter Notebook environment. The NFDI4Biodiversity YouTube Channel and Zenodo Community are used to publish Open Educational Resources.

Finally, choosing the appropriate format for this is critical to its success. Depending on the learning objectives and audience a variety of formats with varying intensity were tested as described above ([Section 3.b](#), [Section 6](#)). Based on that experiences, the following modules and programs form the NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio:

1. Seasonal Schools

- Intense training (1-2 weeks) on specific topics with a limited number of participants. This training is organised as cooperation between TA1M4 and partner institutions and provides training for tools and teaching with data for specific target groups.

2. Support of external training programs

- NFDI4Biodiversity supports training programs that are not offered by the consortium itself such as *Data Train* and *MarMic*. These yearly training programs for PhD students cover the entire data value chain and are designed to contribute to data literacy training in both the scientific and private sectors. NFDI4Biodiversity supports these programs in terms of lectures about general RDM topics as well as tools and services, and event moderation ([Supplementary Table 3](#)).

3. Individual events

- 1-4 hours lectures or workshops that can be requested by everyone who is interested in RDM via the NFDI4Biodiversity helpdesk. They can also be implemented into universities' curricula e.g. as part of a B.Sc. or M.Sc module. The lectures contain varying content ranging from RDM basics and an introduction into the NFDI to services and tools provided by NFDI4Biodiversity. The lectures are realised by partner organisations (e.g. GFBio e.V., PANGAEA) and are coordinated by the training coordinator ([Supplementary Table 3](#)).

4. Training on legal aspects

- These workshops focus on specific challenges in handling biodiversity and environmental data and thus support partner institutions. Further, TA1M4 currently works on publishing a podcast regarding the experiences gained in the workshops.

5. Workshops on Tools and Services

- These training offers are organised and realised by the service providers on a regular basis and provide support for the NFDI4Biodiversity services (e.g. GFBio DMP-Tool, Submission Service, BEXIS2, BIIGLE, Terminology Service, VAT, DWB) ([Supplementary Table 3](#)).

6. Workshops for trainers

- *Train the Trainer* workshops equip trainers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively train others. The workshops are planned based on the concept developed by FDMentor [27].

7. Open Educational Resources -OER can be made available online for students and researchers to access on their own time, allowing them to learn at their own pace.

- *Self-Learning Unit (SLU)* - The SLU provides a practical introduction to scientific data management for self-study and teaching and will be further developed and updated on a regular basis.

- *Slides* - NFDI4Biodiversity started to publish slides for lecturers that can be integrated into teaching. They are based on the GFBio Roadshow format and will be further developed and updated on a regular basis.
- *Videos* - NFDI4Biodiversity constantly expands video content (Data Science 4 Ecologists, RDM for Ecologists, VAT) by publishing recordings of different training events e.g. Winter School 2022, workshop *Who owns my data?*.

b. Quality management

Quality management is essential for training and education services. The NFDI4Biodiversity quality concept is developed by the Service Coordinator, as well as Special Interest Group 2 Service Monitoring and FAIRness (SIG2 Service). The implementation is monitored in TA1M5 (regular quality surveys, user feedback, quality management, reputation systems). The concept follows best practices of the HeFDI quality assurance concept [28] and community-based standards, ensuring that the content meets common standards in biodiversity research.

To promote active and up-to-date learning, contact with service providers is established, and networking with relevant initiatives and institutions is prioritised. Quality evaluation is conducted through onboarding processes, involving service providers in ongoing monitoring and continuous quality control. From 2024 on, annual performance reviews will be performed to ensure quality improvement.

This process ensures (1) that the training is tailored to the needs of the participants, (2) that clear learning objectives are defined, and (3) that all necessary materials are available to support the training events now and in the future.

Teaching materials are designed and deposited as OER, allowing easy access and reuse. Feedback offers are provided to evaluate fitness and usefulness. Quality parameters and feedback possibilities are developed and integrated on different levels, and statistical analysis and evaluations are conducted to assess event success and identify areas for improvement.

Regular performance reviews and analysis of experiences contribute to the quality improvement process. KPIs and evaluation results are collected, communicated, and incorporated into quality assurance concepts by the SIG2 Service and SIG3 Training.

c. Resources

NFDI4Biodiversity training has a dedicated annual budget for costs relating to events and trainers. This budget, managed by the Steering Committee and the SIG3 Training, was not fully used in 2020-2022 since training events were delivered online only. In 2022 the budget was used to cover costs for external experts in the workshops on legal aspects. Events can strongly benefit from external professionals in order to share experiences and gain expertise in topics that the partner network is not fully familiar with. These events can also serve as a platform for presenting the project's results and achievements, e.g. workshop at the GfÖ Conference 2022.

In 2023-2025, it is planned to use the budget for creating training materials, providing partner support, organising events and covering costs for the teaching

environment Klaxoon. Klaxoon is a visual workspace that can improve collaborative work and quality assessment during training sessions. The tool was successfully piloted in the RDM Workshop at BTU in May 2023 ([Supplementary Table 3](#)). We currently possess one licence to test the scope of the software but we would like to make this tool available to more partners in the future.

d. Marketing

Marketing is another key aspect for transferring knowledge and tools to the community, as well as generating support from stakeholders. The primary goal is to increase the visibility and accessibility and attractiveness of training offers and teaching materials. Public relations is done in close cooperation with the Public Relations coordinator and SIG1 PR-Team. It is essential to increase awareness and accessibility of training activities, tools/services, and training materials. The marketing strategy considers several processes: website integration, workflows, platforms and usability. This includes integrating sign-up forms, social media feeds, and other tools in order to optimise usability. This further involves designing user-friendly experiences that make it easy to find and engage with relevant content and offerings. One key element of NFDI4Biodiversity marketing efforts is promoting existing and future training activities on the NFDI4Biodiversity website [29], developing workflows for announcing events via different communication channels such as NFDI4Biodiversity website, Twitter [30], and Forschungsdaten.Info [31] and advertising training material for services and tools.

These processes are important to promote training activities and boost collaboration with stakeholders and non-consortial initiatives. To achieve this, the consortium collaborates with other NFDI consortia and initiatives beyond NFDI to create synergies and avoid duplication of development efforts. Co-marketing collaborations with the FDMentor *Train-the-Trainer Program on Research Data Management*, the *Certificate Course in Research Data Management* by fdm.nrw, Information Centre for Life Sciences (ZB-MED) or the curricular module *Research Data Management* by the University of Bielefeld. We also build relations with international initiatives e.g., ELIXIR and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Society for open, reliable, and transparent ecology and evolutionary biology (SORTEE), via representation in working groups and events and advertising offers within the NFDI4Biodiversity network.

5. Management and Governance of Training activities

For the coordination and monitoring of training activities, the position of a training coordinator has been established at the joint project office of GFBio e.V. and UniBremen/MARUM in Bremen. The position of the training coordinator has been held by Dr. Daniel Tschink since October 2021. His tasks include:

- to gather training offers provided by the partner of NFDI4Biodiversity
- to consolidate training offers into an NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio
- to align the training portfolio and material to common community standards (cross-cutting topics)
- to support and promote training activities

The governance of training activities is in the hands of the Steering Committee. This committee is responsible for strategic decision-making and providing overall guidance for the community's activities. For portfolio and strategy development, the Steering Committee has established the SIG3 Training in March 2022. SIG's are internal Think Tanks dealing with cross-cutting topics across Task Areas and Measures. They prepare decisions for the Steering committee or provide recommendations for action. The task of SIG3 Training is to create innovations and synergies between the various organisational structures and interest groups in the consortium. For instance, to develop and promote NFDI4Biodiversity training, SIG3 Training closely cooperates with SIG1 PR-Team and SIG2 Service. SIG3 Training developed a comprehensive concept for training and education in NFDI4Biodiversity as described in [Section 4](#). The Training Coordinator is Chair of SIG3 Training and in this capacity also a member of the NFI4Biodiversity Steering Committee. This allows for direct communication and efficient decision-making regarding training activities.

The conceptualization and realisation of training activities within the NFDI4Biodiversity community is further done through the collaboration in various Task Areas and Measures. They enable the community to address specific needs and challenges within the biodiversity research field as they are composed of representatives of the partner institutions and serve as members of the special interest groups as well as the Steering Committee.

NFDI4Biodiversity training activities are planned in several Measures of TA1 (2involve) and are linked to work in TA3 (2consolidate) and TA4 (4all & 4future). By coordinating training and education activities across Task Areas the Training Coordinator can help to raise awareness of the value of effective data management practices and the importance of data literacy in all work programme activities of the consortium.

6. Training activities implemented in the work programme

The work programme of NFDI4Biodiversity comprises 5 Task Areas with multiple Measures that aim to promote access to interoperable data. This Section provides an overview of the objectives, outputs, and planned activities of Measures that have specific training-related milestones during the initial funding period ([Supplementary Table 2](#)).

a. Task Area 1 Measure 2 - Support with tools/platforms for (early) mobilisation of data and data analyses

NFDI4Biodiversity aims to support the early mobilisation of biodiversity data and facilitate its entry into the DLC through the use of tools and services. TA1M2 supports users by recommending tools that fulfil common standards in data acquisition through their expertise in bioinformatics, ecoinformatics, biodiversity informatics, and general data management. TA1M2 provides regular and on-demand training and technical support to users with widely used, preferably generic tools for data management and transformation (M1.2.4, [Supplementary Table 2](#)). These trainings are either organised as individual workshops or embedded into NFDI4Biodiversity training offers such as Winter School 2022. The goal for the first funding period is to develop and teach a workflow for data mobilisation and analysis using NFDI4Biodiversity tools/platforms. To achieve this, TA1M2 focuses on creating training content that is relevant, engaging, and actionable, while also emphasising the key messages that participants should take home from the training. In addition, the Measure will implement strategies to assess and improve the quality of our training, such as regular evaluations and feedback sessions developed by SIG2 Service and SIG3 Training, as well as ongoing professional development for our trainers. Ultimately, the aim is to not only provide valuable knowledge and skills, but also inspires and empowers participants to apply what they have learned in their daily work. Thus, the measure provides and improves tools and platforms that researchers already use. E.g. in the context of the NFDI4Biodiversity Winter School 2022, TA1M2 did set up a Jupyter instance on the de.NBI cloud infrastructure. Thus, participants could be provided with a hands-on learning experience.

b. Task Area 1 Measure 3 - Front office/back office: Active Research Data Management (RDM) & data science support

TA1M3 focuses on the active support of RDM and data science. This measure coordinates the helpdesk activities, providing assistance to users. It handles support requests related to DMPs, data submission, and service support (M1.3.1, [Supplementary Table 2](#)). The helpdesk further acts as a central point for support requests, including those related to training needs and resources e.g. individual lectures. As NFDI4Biodiversity progresses, the aim is to expand the expert network within the helpdesk in order to expand the fields of expertise e.g. support for ethical and legal aspects in biodiversity research. This expansion involves experts from partner institutions and incorporating local support personnel and services offered by initiatives at the regional level or other NFDI consortia within the broader network (M1.3.2, [Supplementary Table 2](#)). By coordinating these efforts, TA1M3 ensures robust and comprehensive support for RDM and data science needs within NFDI4Biodiversity.

c. Task Area 1 Measure 4 - Education and training

TA1M4 focuses on the establishment of FAIR research data management as a core topic in biodiversity-related undergraduate and graduate curricula at German universities and organises training on all phases of the DLC. The Measure also provides teaching material (such as the SLU, training videos [32]) that are available to researchers, citizen scientists, and students (M1.4.1, [Supplementary Table 2](#)). Further, together with TA1M2 we aim to mediate hands-on knowledge on the services and tools provided by NFDI4Biodiversity and to sharpen the RDM skills of the different target groups.

The main target groups of these offers are individual researchers, mainly graduate students, PhD students and Postdocs, but also multipliers, including various biodiversity research infrastructures, universities, and botanical and zoological societies. Further, TA1M4 emphasises the importance of connecting the consortium-specific trainings and materials with other NFDI-consortia and with overarching NFDI-services in education and training as part of the consortium's engagement in cross-cutting topics.

Training events are an important component of professional development, allowing individuals to acquire new skills, knowledge and expertise in their field. Two types of training events that have proven to be particularly beneficial in recent years were organised by TA1M4, the Winter School 2022 and Workshops on legal aspects. By attending these events, participants were able to expand their knowledge and skills, network with other professionals in their field, and gain valuable insights into the latest developments. The implementation of real data from the use case PlantHub (TA1M1) could further illustrate the trained concepts on real case studies from our partner iDiv (M1.4.2, [Supplementary Table 2](#)). The integration of such case studies into university teaching, e.g. by using example metadata sets, will be part of the next project months (M1.4.2, [Supplementary Table 2](#)).

Beyond training events, TA1M4 successfully achieved the milestone of "Outreach to multiplier communities established" (M1.4.4, [Supplementary Table 2](#)) through its effective strategy of conference participation. By actively engaging in community conferences like the GfÖ Annual Conference 2022 through poster sessions and workshops, TA1M4 not only disseminated information and knowledge to a wider audience but also reached out to multiplier communities. These interactions enabled the team to teach valuable RDM skills and conduct needs assessment while fostering national and international networking opportunities.

The goal for the first funding period is to further standardise training opportunities offered by the consortium to ensure high-quality learning experiences for all participants. This includes for example the development of standardised training offerings such as the NFDI4Biodiversity RDM Workshop and Seasonal Schools. Additionally, a standard program will be offered for the development of coding competencies and research software. The Measure also aims to pilot and implement service-specific training offerings together with TA1M2 and TA3M1 and implement marketing strategies for training material e.g. SLU, lecture slides together that can be embedded into the Data Literacy Alliance (DALIA) training platform currently developed. To ensure that our training is relevant and effective, TA1M4 plans to adapt the RDM competencies matrix (DINI/nestor AG Forschungsdaten UAG Schulungen/Fortbildungen) [33] to the specific needs in biodiversity related research. Moreover, TA1M4 aims to expand the availability of training datasets, which were piloted during the Winter School, to a wider audience. Another key objective is to provide hands-on tools and services for

teaching. This includes e.g. community access to the service JupyterHub that was set up for the Winter School 2022.

d. Task Area 3 Measure 1 - Identification and description of the current and emerging technical ecosystem in biodiversity research

The focus of this Measure is the description and categorization of tools and services provided by NFDI4Biodiversity partners, targeting a broad user community, technical experts, and experienced domain-specific data scientists. The services provided by the network cover a range of aspects related to biodiversity research and data management. This includes tasks such as data curation and harmonisation, quality assurance, FAIRness, promoting reproducibility, facilitating publication, long-term preservation, and archiving of data products and software code. Identifying and describing this common technical ecosystem can help to ensure that everyone within the community is using the same tools and technologies, which can improve collaboration and communication. As our network continues to expand, the collection and classification of services remain in the process of consolidation. Once all services are collected and classified, KPIs will be complemented to further monitor and improve the quality of the services together with SIG2 Service. By monitoring these KPIs, the network can identify areas for improvement and the technologies and tools that are most commonly used, Task Areas Members (e.g. TA1M4) can better understand where they may need to invest in additional training to ensure that everyone has the skills and knowledge needed. Another result of this Measure is to consolidate and adapt existing work of the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI). de.NBI is collaborating with NFDI4Biodiversity in terms of training and services such as using the de.NBI cloud infrastructure at the Winter School 2022. Further, during the de.NBI Spring School 2023, GFBio e.V. and PANGAEA have achieved a significant milestone by teaming up with other consortia, such as PUNCH4NFDI and NFDI4Microbiota, to offer a comprehensive training program covering the basics of research data management as well as the tools and services provided by the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium (M3.1.2, [Supplementary Table 2](#)).

e. Task Area 4 Measure 4 - Software application frameworks

TA4M4 aims to provide scientists with the necessary frameworks and services to conduct data-driven research collaboratively in the Research Data Commons (RDC). The measure includes powerful tools for processing, analysis, and visualisation, as well as generic tools to foster collaboration among researchers. These services will be hosted in the RDC cloud storage, making them easily accessible to researchers without technical and administrative issues.

Continuous training is important to empower users with various skills and scientific backgrounds to take full advantage of the frameworks and services in their daily work. As the RDC is not fully operational yet, the training for external users has just been started (M4.4.3, [Supplementary Table 2](#)). So far, two internal API workshops for developers (Core Storage) have taken place.

The goal for the first funding period is to develop training material and courses for software developers, data users/providers as soon as the RDC is fully operational. Furthermore, TA4M4 originally aimed to establish and operate a training and support platform in close collaboration with TA1M4 (Education and Training). This task has been shifted due to recent developments in NFDI. The Technical University Darmstadt (TU Darmstadt) currently develops a common training platform for all NFDI consortia as part of the DALIA project [34]. This platform is expected to be

handed over to the Section EduTrain by the end of 2025. To meet the objective of a national offering, the training portfolio of NFDI4Biodiversity will be standardised and integrated into the DALIA platform after project completion. The current efforts in consolidating and advertising NFDI4Biodiversity training is focused on embedding the training portfolio into the NFDI4Biodiversity website (see chapter 3.3.4 Marketing), the Zenodo platform and the YouTube channels.

7. List of abbreviations

AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut - Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung / Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research
BASS	Biogeochemical processes and Air-sea exchange in the Sea-Surface microlayer
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung / Federal Ministry of Education and Research
BTU	Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus-Senftenberg / Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg
bw2FDM	Baden-württembergisches Begleit- und Weiterentwicklungsprojekt für Forschungsdatenmanagement / Baden-Württemberg support and further development for research data management
DALIA	Data Literacy Alliance
de.NBI	Deutsches Netzwerk für Bioinformatik-Infrastruktur / German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft / German Research Foundation
DINI	Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation e. V. / German Initiative for Network Information
DLC	Data Life Cycle
DMP	Data Management Plan
DWB	Diversity Workbench
ECPGR	European Cooperative Programme for Plant Genetic Resources
ELIXIR	European life sciences infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
fdm.nrw	Landesinitiative für Forschungsdatenmanagement Nordrhein Westfalen / State Initiative for Research Data Management North Rhine-Westphalia
FEaA	Forschungsinitiative zum Erhalt der Artenvielfalt / Research initiative for the conservation of biodiversity
GEOMAR	GEOMAR - Helmholtz Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel / GEOMAR - Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
GFBio	German Federation for Biological Data
GfÖ	Gesellschaft für Ökologie e.V. / Ecological Society of Germany, Austria and Switzerland
HeFDI	Hessische Forschungsdateninfrastrukturen / Hessian Research Data Infrastructures
ICBM	Institut für Chemie und Biologie des Meere / Institute for Chemistry and Biology of the Marine Environment
IMPRS	International Max Planck Research School of Marine Microbiology
IPK	Leibniz Institut für Pflanzengenetik und Kulturpflanzenforschung / Leibniz Institute of plant genetics and crop plant research

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Measure
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur/National Research Data Infrastructure
OER	Open Educational Resources
RDC	Research Data Commons
RDM	Research data management
Section EduTrain	NFDI Section Training and Education
SIG2 Service	Special Interest Group 2 Service Monitoring and FAIRness
SIG3 Training	Special Interest Group 3 Training and Education
SLU	Self-Learning Unit
SNSB	Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns / Bavarian Natural History Collections
SORTEE	Society for open, reliable, and transparent ecology and evolutionary biology
TA	Task Area
TKFDM	Thüringer Kompetenznetzwerk Forschungsdatenmanagement / Thuringian Competence Network for Research Data Management
TU Darmstadt	Technischen Universität Darmstadt / Technical University Darmstadt
UBRA	University Bremen Research Alliance
UfU	Unabhängiges Institut für Umweltfragen e.V. / Independent Institute for Environmental Issues
UFZ	Helmholtz Zentrum für Umweltforschung / Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research
VAT	Visualization, Analysis and Transformation System
ZB-MED	Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften / Information Centre for Life Sciences
ZMT	Leibniz-Zentrum für Marine Tropenforschung / Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research

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9. Supplementary material

Supplementary Table 1 List of partners involved in training and education

This table briefly introduces the current collaborations for training activities in alphabetic order. It shows the wide and diversity of our partnerships, how they contribute to the training within the network and their way of supplementing each other.

Abbreviation	Institution	Role in NFDI4Biodiversity Training
BIBI	Bielefeld Institute for Bioinformatics Infrastructure at Bielefeld University	BIBI contributes to the BMBF funded infrastructure de.NBI to provide comprehensive state-of-the-art bioinformatics services such as BIIGLE and thus contribute to the training portfolio. Furthermore, they foster cooperation of the German bioinformatics community with international bioinformatics network structures such as ELIXIR.
de.NBI	deutsches Netzwerk für Bioinformatik-Infrastruktur	de.NBI organizes training events, such as the de.NBI Spring School 2023, and provides online training materials for a broad range of topics in bioinformatics. Furthermore, de.NBI provides a cloud infrastructure that is used in NFDI4Biodiversity training activities.
GFBio e.V.	Gesellschaft für biologische Daten e.V.	GFBio e.V. 's main objectives are building and supporting an active network of experts and infrastructures as well as providing a single point of contact for a rich portfolio of services, covering the whole DLC, from data management plans to data publication. Furthermore, GFBio e.V. coordinates NFDI4Biodiversity education and training activities via the training coordinator.
GfÖ	Gesellschaft für Ökologie e.V.	GfÖ is one of the world's largest societies for scientific ecology and opens access to a large ecological community. GfÖ contributes to training activities, outreach, user feedback and cultural change and was a partner in the Winter School 2022.
HITS	Heidelberger Institut für Theoretische Studien gGmbH	HITS conducts basic research with a focus on the processing, structuring, and analysing of large amounts of complex data and the development of computational methods and software. HITS contributes in NFDI4Biodiversity training with their experience in serving projects with tools for the first mile of data management. This includes the

		RightField tool for data annotation and OpenRefine. These tools were trained at the Winter School 2022.
IPK	Leibniz-Institut für Pflanzengenetik und Kulturpflanzenforschung Gatersleben	IPK focuses on the elucidation of the fundamental principles of evolution, development and adaptation operating in our leading crop plants – cereals, grain legumes and oilseed plants. The IPK Gatersleben contributes its experience in managing plant biodiversity data and plant phenotyping data as well as the collaboration within national networks like de.NBI as well as international networks like ELIXIR and the ECPGR. Further, it provides training courses and offers expertise about the implementation of integrated biological information systems as well as in the provision of bioinformatic tools.
University Bremen / MARUM	Zentrum für Marine Umweltwissenschaften der Universität Bremen	MARUM is the home of the DFG Cluster of Excellence <i>The Ocean Floor – Earth's Uncharted Interface</i> as well as national and international research projects. MARUM in collaboration with the AWI, operates the Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science PANGAEA as a permanent facility. MARUM and PANGAEA contribute to NFDI4Biodiversity training portfolio with several training programs such as MarMic, UBRA/Data Train, PANGAEA training and are the most important partner next to University Marburg.
University Jena / iDiv	Universität Jena	University Jena is one of the three universities which form together with the UFZ the core of the DFG Research Center for Integrative Biodiversity Research, iDiv. The University provides expertise in data management of large biodiversity projects including the Biodiversity Exploratories, the Jena Experiment and as well as the development of the BEXIS2 data management platform. University Jena supports consultation and training on research data management leveraging semantic techniques for RDM, provenance for scientific data and workflows as well as support for BEXIS2. Further, Uni Jena offers the Master Course <i>Management of Scientific Data</i> (6 ECTS).
University Kassel	Universität Kassel	The University of Kassel is known for its multi-layered approach to education and research in Germany. The university has a range of competences across the fields

		of nature and technology, culture, and society. In NFDI4Biodiversity training, University Kassel functions as a model institution for facilitating RDM as part of universities curricula.
University Marburg	Philipps-Universität Marburg	University Marburg offers an interdisciplinary biodiversity research environment with 17+ working groups focused on ecology, climate research, and computer science. The university's database research group is leading the development of the VAT system for biodiversity and environmental data visualization, analysis, and transformation. They have also established a local service center for e-research to support scientists in digitally assisted research. University Marburg leads the joint Hessian-wide project HeFDI, promoting coordinated research data support across 11 universities and universities of applied sciences. Moreover, University Marburg is part of the Data Literacy Education network, driven by the Stifterverband, and collaborates within NFDI4Biodiversity, aiming for seamless integration of VAT and Jupyter Notebooks. The university provides training and education sources, publishes case studies for universities, and holds the Lead of TA1M4 by Ortrun Brand.
SGN	Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung	SGN is a natural history collection and GFBio data center for archiving and publishing biodiversity data. SGN contributes curatorial and technical services and expertise and operates biological collection databases. SGN supports training activities, such as Winter School 2022, with their expertise in data submission and search services as well as in terminologies and ontologies.
SNSB	Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns	SNSB is one of the largest research institutions for natural history in Germany. The mission comprises research activities in the field of biodiversity informatics and software engineering in the field of bio- and geodiversity data management and processing. SNSB offers training and support regarding the tool Diversity Workbench (DWB).

SUB	Niedersächsische Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen	The SUB is one of the largest libraries in Germany, a leader in the development of digital libraries and involved in national and international networks and other NFDIs. In NFDI4Biodiversity, the SUB contributes to outreach-related activities and training activities with respect to legal and ethical aspects, like licensing and copyrights (TA1M4 - Training) and TA4M5 - RDC Governance.
University Göttingen / CIDAS	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen	The CIDAS is a central scientific unit at the University Göttingen that facilitates interdisciplinary collaboration and activities in the field of data science. CIDAS focuses on coordinating and advancing research, teaching, and knowledge transfer. The University Göttingen created a YouTube video series on data science for NFDI4Biodiversity and supported the Winter School 2022 as well as the development of the SLU.

Supplementary Table 2 Status of milestones dedicated to training

This table summarizes the current status of milestones dedicated to training.

<i>Milestone</i>	<i>Milestone Description</i>	<i>Start of work</i>	<i>Target Month</i>	<i>Status</i>
Task Area 1 Measure 2 - Support with tools/platforms				
M1.2.4	RDM tool and platform support in accordance with NFDI-RDC	28	48	not started yet
Task Area 1 Measure 3 - Front office/back office: Active Research Data Management (RDM) & data science support				
M1.3.1	Back-office operational, ticket system unified and consortium trained	06	18	complete
M1.3.2	Training workshops for front-office personnel at universities and institutes- Training 1	15	21	complete
	Training workshops for front-office personnel at universities and institutes- Training 2	21	40	in progress
	Training workshops for front-office personnel at universities and institutes- Training 3	40	60	not started yet
Task Area 1 Measure 4 - Education and training				

M1.4.1	First training datasets and teaching videos available	14	24	complete
M1.4.2	Design of case studies in collaboration with other NFDIs and TA1M1 use cases	15	30	in progress
M1.4.3	First case studies are incorporated into university teaching	24	42	in progress
M1.4.4	Outreach to multiplier communities established	24	48	in progress
M1.4.5	Revision of case studies based on first practical experiences	48	60	not started yet
Task Area 3 Measure 1 - Identification and description of the technical ecosystem in biodiversity research				
M3.1.2	Training events established together with other consortia	13	30	in progress
Task Area 4 Measure 4 - Software application frameworks				
M4.4.3	First training and support platform established and operational	20	36	shifted to DALIA

Supplementary Table 3 List of training activities 2021-2023

This table contains a detailed list of training events conducted during the last three project years. The list covers the period 2021 to July 2023. It further contains four events that are already planned for August to October 2023. A summary of the list including number of participants is shown in Table 1.

Month	Description	Category
January 2021	MarMic Research Data Management module, University of Bremen ; F.O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov, J.Linares	Workshop
April 2021	41st Diversity Workbench Workshop - SNSB. Project presentation, M. Friedrichs-Manthey; Training with two use cases from NFDI4Biodiversity; D. Triebel, P. Grobe, H. Höfer	Workshop
June 2021	FEEdA - Forschungsinitiative zum Erhalt der Artenvielfalt, Data Management Workshop with GFBio and NFDI4Biodiversity	Workshop
	Taxon-OMICS Schwerpunktprogramm, Data Management Workshop with GFBio and NFDI4Biodiversity	Workshop
July 2021	NFDI4Biodiversity TA1 Community Workshop: Tools und services von GFBio	Workshop
	NFDI4Biodiversity TA1 Community Workshop Rechtsfragen I: Rechtliche Fragen der Datennutzung	Workshop
	U Bremen research Alliance Data Steward Track - How to write a data management plan?; F.O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov, J. Linares, T. Weibulat	Presentation

August 2021	GfÖ Annual Conference - pre-meeting workshop <i>The 101 of data management</i> with GFBio and NFDI4Biodiversity: J. Weber, J. Linares	Workshop
October 2021	FDM-Zertifikatskurs fdm.nrw - Modul 3; NFDI4Biodiversity contribution: F. O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov	Presentation
November 2021	42. Diversity Workbench Workshop, SNSB	Workshop
January 2022	MarMic Research Data Management module; F.O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov, J. Linares	Workshop
	Research Data Management Lecture at the University Oldenburg by D. Tschink, J. Linares	Presentation
March 2022	Data Train Lecture <i>Data and information management</i> by I. Kostadinov, F.O. Glöckner	Presentation
April 2022	2. Workshop Forschungsdatenmanagement für FEa BiodiWert Projekte - NFDI4Biodiversity und KonsortSWD	Workshop
May 2022	NFDI4Biodiversity TA1 Community Workshop Rechtsfragen II: Konkrete Anwendungen und Herausforderungen beim Umgang mit dem Umweltinformaionsgesetz	Workshop
	Data Train <i>Overview about programming languages</i> by D. Tschink	Moderation
June 2022	Data Train Workshop - together with UBRA, Bremen	Workshop
	43. Diversity Workbench Workshop, SNSB	Workshop
October 2022	BEXIS2 Workshop at RESEARCH DATA@RMU 2022	Workshop
	FDM-Zertifikatskurs fdm.nrw - Modul 3; NFDI4Biodiversity contribution: F. O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov	Presentation
	NFDI ToolTalk: BEXIS2 Research Data Management System by R. Gerlach, J. Gaikwad	Presentation
November 2022	GfÖ Annual Conference - pre-meeting workshop: How to better manage your data - and thereby enrich research	Workshop
	Who owns my data? On our way to open data - Nagoya and beyond!	Workshop
December 2022	NFDI4Biodiversity - GfÖ Winter School on Data Management in Ecology and Environmental Science	Seasonal School
	PANGAEA Community Workshop	Workshop
January 2023	RDM Lecture at the University Oldenburg by D. Tschink, J. Linares	Presentation
	MarMic Research Data Management module; F.O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov, J.Linares	Workshop
February 2023	BASS Workshop at GEOMAR by D. Tschink, J. Linares, M. Oellermann	Workshop
March 2023	Workshop at IPK/de.NBI Spring School by D. Tschink, J. Linares, M. Oellermann, L. Möller	Workshop
	Data Train <i>Data and information management</i> by I. Kostadinov, F.O. Glöckner	Presentation
April 2023	Data Train <i>Managing qualitative data</i> by D. Tschink	Moderation

	Workshop zur Bild- und Videoannotationssoftware BIIGLE - BIBI/Uni Bielefeld	Workshop
April-July 2023	Module: Research Data Management, lecture, exercise and seminar as part of the BSc Education Marine Geosciences, University of Bremen. F.O. Glöckner, I Kostadinov, R. Huber, L Möller et al.	
May 2023	Research Data Management - Biodiversity and Environmental Science Workshop at Brandenburg University of Technology by D. Tschink, J. Linares, M. Oellermann, B. Gemeinholzer	Workshop
	Data Train Moderation <i>Overview about programming languages</i> by D. Tschink	Moderation
	PANGAEA Community Workshop	Workshop
July 2023	Coffee Lecture: BEXIS2 - Forschungsdatenmanagement in Verbundprojekten	Workshop
August 2023	44. Diversity Workbench-Workshop, SNSB	Workshop
September 2023	GfÖ Annual Conference - pre-meeting workshop: How to better manage your data - and thereby enrich research	Workshop
October 2023	FDM-Zertifikatskurs fdm.nrw - Modul 3; NFDI4Biodiversity contribution: F. O. Glöckner, I. Kostadinov	Presentation
November 2023	SORTEE Webinar by M. Oellermann	Presentation